

Program

Second IP & Innovation Researchers of Asia (IPIRA) Conference

27 - 28 February 2020

&

Workshop for IP Teachers and Researchers

29 February 2020

Faculty of Law, Universitas Indonesia

Welcome Message

Dear Colleagues,

Welcome to the Second IP & Innovation Researchers of Asia (IPIRA) Conference and Workshop for IP Teachers and Researchers, held at the Faculty of Law, Universitas Indonesia!

IPIRA was created in 2019 as an annual initiative of the IP & Innovation Researchers of Asia Network, to provide a forum for intellectual exchanges between researchers interested in IP and Innovation law in Asia and beyond. IPIRA is proud to welcome researchers from all nationalities and levels of seniority, to meet and discuss their works-in-progress. Like the 2019 edition, the Second IPIRA Conference includes a workshop for researchers to discuss and share their respective research topics and methodologies. We trust that this initiative would offer an active venue for sharing the ever-growing body of knowledge in the field of IP and Innovation.

The Organizers would like to extend their sincere thanks to the presenters, chairs, and participants of the Conference and Workshop, many of whom have travelled long distances. We feel honored to host you at the Second IPIRA Conference! We are also much honored and would like to thank our distinguished Keynote Speakers. As always, the conference and workshop would not be possible without the tireless efforts of our colleagues, staff, and student assistants. We thank them warmly. We also extend our gratitude to the colleagues at the Faculty of Law, Universitas Indonesia, for hosting the second edition of IPIRA Conference. We also thank the International Trademark Association (INTA) for its continuous endeavors to support to this event and for sponsoring the closing reception.

We trust that you will find the next three days insightful, and will enjoy discussing IP-related topics, catching-up with old friends, and meeting new ones. Once again, thank you for making this event special and for enriching discussions about IP and innovation with your research and works-in-progress.

The Organizers of the Second IPIRA Conference and Workshop for IP Teachers and Researchers

Conference Program

THURSDAY, 27 FEBRUARY 2020 (DAY 1)

8.00am – 9.00am **REGISTRATION**
Foyer Balai Sidang Djokosaetono

OPENING OF THE DAY

Balai Sidang Djokosaetono

9.00am – 9.05am SINGING OF THE INDONESIAN NATIONAL ANTHEM

9.05am – 9.15am ***Welcome Remarks***
PROFESSOR **ARI KUNCORO**
RECTOR, UNIVERSITAS INDONESIA

9.15am – 9.30 am ***Introduction by Organizers***
AGUS SARDJONO, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS INDONESIA
MOHAMED ABDERRAOUF BDIYOU, WIPO ACADEMY, WORLD INTELLECTUAL
PROPERTY ORGANIZATION
ANTONY TAUBMAN, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY, GOVERNMENT PROCUREMENT AND
COMPETITION DIVISION, WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION
IRENE CALBOLI, TEXAS A&M UNIVERSITY SCHOOL OF LAW AND SCHOOL OF LAW,
UNIVERSITY OF GENEVA
JACQUES DE WERRA, SCHOOL OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF GENEVA

KEYNOTE PRESENTATION

Balai Sidang Djokosaetono

9.30am – 10.15am DR. **FREDDY HARRIS (TBC)**
DIRECTOR GENERAL OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY
MINISTRY OF LAW AND HUMAN RIGHTS

10.15am – 10.25am PHOTO SESSION (*Staircase of the Auditorium Djokosoetono*)

10.25am – 10.55am **Morning Tea Break** (*Auditorium Djokosoetono*)

PARALLEL SESSIONS (1)

10.55am – 1.00pm

Balai Sidang

Djokosaetono

PARALLEL SESSION 1.A: ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, BLOCKCHAIN, AND INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

CHAIR

IDA MADIEHA ABDUL GHANI AZMI, AHMAD IBRAHIM KULLIYAH OF LAWS, INTERNATIONAL ISLAMIC UNIVERSITY MALAYSIA

PRESENTERS

VIJAY MAKYAM KUMAR, I-WIN IP SERVICE

Use of Blockchain Technology in Intellectual Property Rights Management and Required Legislative Framework-An Indian Perspective

PRAGYAN DEEP AGARWAL, THE CENTRE FOR WTO STUDIES, MINISTRY OF COMMERCE

Blockchaining Copyright to Free the Intermediaries: Analysing Prospects and Evaluating Challenges

TATSUHIRO UENO, LAW SCHOOL, WASEDA UNIVERSITY

Copyright Exception for Text-and-Data Mining: Japan as “Paradise for Machine Learning”

DEBMITA MONDAL, HIDAYATULLAH NATIONAL LAW UNIVERSITY, RAIPUR

Interface between Blockchain Technology and Copyright: Locking horns over Digital Content

DILAN THAMPAPILLAI, COLLEGE OF LAW, NATIONAL AUSTRALIA UNIVERSITY

Artificial Intelligence and the Unravelling of Copyright Law

10.55am – 1.00pm

C 105

PARALLEL SESSION 1.B: INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS, INNOVATION, AND TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER

CHAIR

GREGORY N. MANDEL, BEASLEY SCHOOL OF LAW, TEMPLE UNIVERSITY

PRESENTERS

SATHYAN BALACHANDRAN, TAMIL NADU NATIONAL LAW UNIVERSITY

Intellectual Property Rights as a Facilitator of Technology Transfer

FENNIKA KRISTIANO, PRESIDENT UNIVERSITY

Promoting Social Enterprises through Partnership in Franchising: Potential Conflict between Franchisor and Franchisee

SHAISTA PEERZADA, A.K.K NEW LAW ACADEMY

Intellectual Property Rights for Innovations in Information Technology

HA LE THI THU, FACULTY OF ECONOMICS AND INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS, FOREIGN TRADE UNIVERSITY

Intellectual Property Management: Case Studies of Japanese and Vietnamese SMEs

IKE FARIDA, FACULTY OF LAW, HITOTSUBASHI UNIVERSITY & **SATYA ARINANTO**, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS INDONESIA

Protection of Information Technology in Industrial 4.0 Era in Indonesia

10.55am – 1.00pm
C 106

PARALLEL SESSION 1.C: INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY, FARMERS' RIGHTS, AND PLANT VARIETIES

CHAIR

K.D. RAJU, RAJIV GANDHI SCHOOL OF IP LAW, IIT KHARAGPUR

PRESENTERS

MASSIMILIANO GRANIERI, DEPARTMENT OF MECHANICAL AND INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF BRESCIA

Sowing and Cultivating the Seed of Diversity in Agri-Food: Intellectual Property Protection in Transnational Perspective

DAVID JEFFERSON, SCHOOL OF LAW, THE UNIVERSITY OF QUEENSLAND

Plant Breeders' Rights Proliferate in Asia: The Spread of the UPOV Convention Model

ASANKA PERERA, MONASH BUSINESS SCHOOL, MONASH UNIVERSITY

Discourse on Realisation of Farmers' Rights in Sri Lanka

ANNAMMA SAMUEL, FACULTY OF LAW, G.D GOENKA UNIVERSITY

Role of Seed Banks in Climate Change Adaptation

SAURAV GHIMIRE, INTERNATIONAL LAW ASSOCIATION, NEPAL BRANCH

Strengthening the Position of Farmers in the Regime of Plant Variety Protection Laws: The Case of Indonesia

10.55am – 1.00pm
Soemadipraja &
Taher

PARALLEL SESSION 1.D: FRAMEWORKS FOR PROTECTION AND ENFORCEMENT OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

CHAIR

MAEGAN MCCANN, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY, GOVERNMENT PROCUREMENT AND COMPETITION DIVISION, WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION

PRESENTERS

HARSHANI GAYANA VIDANAGAMACHCHI, DEPARTMENT OF MASS COMMUNICATION, UNIVERSITY OF KELANIYA

Effect of Regulation for the Protection of Intellectual Property in Sri Lanka

MANJULA MALLEPALLI, SCHOOL OF LAW, BENNETT UNIVERSITY

WTO Dispute Settlement and Retaliation

ZIYAN QIU, GRADUATE SCHOOL OF LAW, NAGOYA UNIVERSITY

Reconsidering the Territoriality Principle in the Context of Transnational Divided Infringement

CATHARINA BUDININGSIH, FACULTY OF LAW, PARAHYANGAN CATHOLIC UNIVERSITY

Under the Pressure of Generalized System of Preferences and TRIPS Plus: Indonesia

VIJAY KUMAR, RAJIV GANDHI SCHOOL OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY LAW, INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, KHARAGPUR

Enforcement of Intellectual Property Rights in Outer Space: Law in Vacuum or in Action?

10.55am – 1.00pm

F 103

PARALLEL SESSION 1.E: GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS: CASE STUDIES

CHAIR

BHUMINDR BUTR-INDR, FACULTY OF LAW, THAMMASAT UNIVERSITY

PRESENTERS

RIA WIERMA PUTRI, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF LAMPUNG

Geographical Indications' Practice in Lampung Province: Case of Lampung Robusta Coffee

LIHINI MADUSHIKA DE SILVA, GENERAL SIR JOHN KOTELAWALA DEFENCE UNIVERSITY

Balancing the Rights of Trademark and Geographical Indication Owners in Sri Lanka: A Social Engineering Task

M. SUNIL GLADSON, SCHOOL OF EXCELLENCE IN LAW, THE TAMIL NADU DR. AMBEDKAR LAW UNIVERSITY

Converting Cultural Property into Monopolistic Intellectual Property and Its Impact on Natural Rights of Cultural Property Owners

RAGINI KHULAKAR, MAHARASHTRA NATIONAL LAW UNIVERSITY, NAGPUR

Issues and Challenges in Implementation of Geographical Indications in India: A Case Study of "Nagpur Oranges" in Maharashtra States

M. RENDI KHUBALKAR, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF SURYAKANCANA CIANJUR

Analysis of Sleeping Geographical Indications in Indonesia

10.55am – 1.00pm

F 104

PARALLEL SESSION 1.F: PATENTS, GENE EDITING AND PUBLIC INTEREST

CHAIR

MASABUMI SUZUKI, GRADUATE SCHOOL OF LAW, NAGOYA UNIVERSITY

PRESENTERS

SACHIN SATHYARAJAN, JINDAL GLOBAL LAW SCHOOL, O.P. JINDAL GLOBAL UNIVERSITY

Genetic Modification Technology Deployment: Intellectual Property and Competition Law Issues Concerning the BT Gene

DUNCAN MATTHEWS, SCHOOL OF LAW, QUEEN MARY UNIVERSITY OF LONDON

New Intellectual Property and Regulatory Approaches to Gene Editing

SARASWATHY VAIDYANATHAN, NATIONAL LAW UNIVERSITY, DELHI

Pharma Licensing Agreements: An Antitrust Perspective

MAMTA RANA, VAISHALI SINGH & G.N. SINHA, SCHOOL OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF PETROLEUM AND ENERGY STUDIES

Assimilating Gene Editing (R)evolution: Cutting Edges and Weaving Threads

WINNER SITORUS, FACULTY OF LAW, HASANUDDIN UNIVERSITY

Local Working as the Embodiment of Public Interest Protection: The Challenge of Indonesian Patent Law

10.55am – 1.00pm

F 105

PARALLEL SESSION 1.G: COPYRIGHT IN THE ONLINE CONTEXT

CHAIR

CATHARINA BUDININGSIH, FACULTY OF LAW, PARAHYANGAN CATHOLIC UNIVERSITY

PRESENTERS

RICCARDO VECELLIO SEGATE, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF MACAU

Ownership and Copyright of Algorithms' End-Products in the EU: How to Cope with Profit Allocation and Artistic Overrepresentation?

MUHAMMAD BILLAH, COLLEGE OF LAW, SULTAN QABOOS UNIVERSITY

Dreaming of a World with Online Open Access for All Books: Can This Dream Become a Reality

LAINA RAFIANTI, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS PADJADJARAN

Intellectual Property and Digital Economy Aspects After the UNESCO Intangible Cultural Heritage Convention: Case Study of Angklung Inscription from Indonesia

ANGWARA CHAIANONG, PRIDI BANOMYONG FACULTY OF LAW, DHURAKIJ PUNDIT UNIVERSITY

Online Copyright Infringement in Thailand Compared with Malaysia, China and USA

RIMA GHOSH, WEST BENGAL NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF JURIDICAL SCIENCES

Digital Rights Management and Indian Copyright Law: A Critical Analysis

1.00pm – 2.30pm

Lunch (*Auditorium Djokosoetono*)

PARALLEL SESSIONS (2)

2:30pm – 4.35pm

Balai Sidang

Djokosoetono

PARALLEL SESSION 2.A: PATENTS AND TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENTS

CHAIR

TAKESHI HISHINUMA, FACULTY OF LAW, NAGOYA GAKUIN UNIVERSITY

PRESENTERS

MOHD DANISH, SCHOOL OF HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES, INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, INDORE

Role of Patent Statistics in the Identification of Valuable Technology: An Analysis Based on Renewal Information

MAS RAHMAH, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS AIRLANGGA

Imposing Disclosure of Origin for Requirement of Patent Registration: Challenges for Implementation

ABDUL ATSAR, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF SINGAPERBANGSA

Patent Quality Legal Audit: Evaluation Model of Conductive Governmental Legal Products for Foreign Investors

APARNA SHARMA, SCHOOL OF HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES, INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, INDORE

Effects of Technological Capabilities and Technological Distance on Foreign Patenting: A Cross-Country Study

RAKHMITA DESMAYANTI, FACULTY OF LAW, TRISAKTI UNIVERSITY

Patent or Trade Secret? The Right Choice for Business Owner

2.30pm – 4.35pm
C 105

PARALLEL SESSION 2.B: INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

CHAIR

MARTIN ADELMAN, GEORGE WASHINGTON UNIVERSITY LAW SCHOOL

PRESENTERS

ENNI SOERJATI, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS PADJADJARAN

The Comparison of Patent on Internet of Things and Artificial Intelligence Regulation between Indonesia and Other Asian Countries

MEERA MATTHEW, SYMBIOSIS LAW SCHOOL, NOIDA

Artificial Intelligence and Rising Legal Loopholes: Need to Redefine Intellectual Property Rights

STEFAN PAPASTEFANOU, BUCERIUS LAW SCHOOL

Machine Learning in Patent Law-Legal Challenges Regarding the Term Invention and Inventor in the Context of Genetic Breeding Algorithms

ANKITA ASERI, NATIONAL LAW UNIVERSITY, JODHPUR & **RAVI PRAKASH RAHUL**, DR. RAM MANOHAR LOHIYA NATIONAL LAW UNIVERSITY, LUCKNOW

Overhauling the Concept of Inventorship in Patent Law Vis-a-Vis AI Invented Patents

DILIP SHARMA, ICFAI LAW SCHOOL, HYDERABAD

Revisiting Intellectual Property Paradigm in the Era of Artificial Intelligence

2.30pm – 4.35pm
C 106

PARALLEL SESSION 2.C: SUI GENERIS SYSTEMS OF PROTECTION: DATABASE, TRADE SECRETS, DESIGN, AND PERSONALITY RIGHTS

CHAIR

ALTHAF MARSOOF, NANYANG BUSINESS SCHOOL, NANYANG TECHNOLOGY UNIVERSITY

PRESENTERS

DENNIS KHONG, CENTRE FOR LAW AND TECHNOLOGY, MULTIMEDIA UNIVERSITY

Database Protection in the Context of Machine Learning: Is There a Market Failure Yet?

ARPAN BANERJEE, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF NEW SOUTH WALES

What Should Trade Secrets Legislation in India Look Like?

MOHAMMED ATAUL KARIM, DEPARTMENT OF LAW, EAST WEST UNIVERSITY

Sui Generis System in International Intellectual Property Regime: Lessons for Bangladesh

SHAHRINA ANIS SAMSUDIN, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITI KEBANGSAAN MALAYSIA

Legal Protection of Indigenous Design in Malaysia: Combination of Laws or Sui Generis?

TWINKLE MAHESHWARY, KIRIT P. MEHTA SCHOOL OF LAW

Personality Rights: The Need for a Separate Legislation

2.30pm – 4.35pm

Soemadipraja &

Taher

PARALLEL SESSION 2.D: INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY AND INNOVATION

CHAIR

SANG JO JONG, SEOUL NATIONAL UNIVERSITY SCHOOL OF LAW

PRESENTERS

WEI WANG, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF HONG KONG

The Neuroscience of Innovation: A Socio-Legal Analysis of Generating University Patents in Asia

RUJITHA SHENOY, NATIONAL LAW UNIVERSITY, ODISHA

Patent Pools and Competition in US, EU & India- Problems & Perspectives

KSHITIJ KUMAR SINGH, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF DELHI

Biomedical Innovation and IPRs: Proprietary Claims Vis-a-Vis Open and Collaborative Model

VALERIY LISITSA, DEPARTMENT OF BUSINESS LAW, CIVIL AND ARBITRATION PROCEDURE, NOVOSIBIRSK STATE UNIVERSITY

The Legal Protection of Investments into Digital Financial Assets: International and National Law Aspects

NOBUYA FUKUGAWA, GRADUATE SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING, TOHOKU UNIVERSITY

Determinants and Impacts of Incorporation of Local Public Technology Transfer Organizations: Evidence from Kohsetsushi of Japan

2.30pm – 4.35pm

F 103

PARALLEL SESSION 2.E: TRADEMARKS AND OVERLAPPING RIGHTS

CHAIR

GEORGE HWANG, GEORGE HWANG LL.C.

PRESENTERS

MD. TOWHINDUL ISLAM, DEPARTMENT OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF DHAKA

Protection of Unregistered Trademarks: Options and Challenges for Businesses in Bangladesh

ERDENECHIMEG DASHPUNTSAG, LAW SCHOOL, OTGONTENGER UNIVERSITY OF MONGOLIA

The Conflict between Trademark and Copyright Protection, and Its Resolution

SUJANA DONANDI SINURAYA, PRESIDENT UNIVERSITY

Benyamin Biang Kerok: A Dispute of Copyright or Trademark?

ALTHAF MARSOOF, NANYANG BUSINESS SCHOOL, NANYANG TECHNOLOGY UNIVERSITY

International IP Standards and Flexibilities: Rethinking Sri Lankan Trademark Law to Achieve Better Compliance while Addressing Domestic Interests

KUHU TIWARI, RAJIV GANDHI SCHOOL OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY LAW, INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, KHARAGPUR

Legal Challenges in Protecting Non-Conventional Pharmaceutical Trademarks in Different Jurisdictions

2.30pm – 4.35pm

F 104

PARALLEL SESSION 2.F: GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS AND DEVELOPMENT

CHAIR

GIORGIO COLOMBO, GRADUATE SCHOOL OF LAW, NAGOYA UNIVERSITY

PRESENTERS

GUSWAN HAKIM, FACULTY OF LAW, HALU OLEO UNIVERSITY

Indigenous People's Rights in the Protection of Geographical Indications in Indonesia

TASLIMA JAHAN, FACULTY OF CORPORATE & INDUSTRIAL LAW, UNITED INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY

Collective Rights on Geographical Indication: Challenges and Opportunity for Development under the Present Legal Framework in Bangladesh

HELITHA MUCHTAR, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS PADJADJARAN

Intellectual Property Protection for Preventing Human Trafficking: The Case of Sumbanese Women and their Woven Clothes

MIRANDA RISANG AYU PALAR, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS PADJADJARAN

The Concept of Communal Intellectual Property Rights in Indonesia

YESSI SERENA RANGKUTI, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS SUMATERA UTARA

Supporting Local Fashion Brand as a Solution to Strengthen Indonesia's Enforcement in Intellectual Property Rights

2.30pm – 4.35pm

F 105

PARALLEL SESSION 2.G: PATENTS AND ACCESS TO MEDICINES

CHAIR

JUSTYNA OZEGALSKA-TRYBALSKA, FACULTY OF LAW, JAGIELLONIAN UNIVERSITY

PRESENTERS

BRYAN MERCURIO, FACULTY OF LAW, CHINESE UNIVERSITY OF HONG KONG

Changing Direction: Promoting a Holistic Approach to Pharmaceutical Patent Law and Policy

KIYOSHI ADACHI, NATIONAL GRADUATE INSTITUTE FOR POLICY STUDIES

An Examination of Selected Public Health Exceptions in Asian Patent Laws

VAN ANH LE, SCHOOL OF LAW, WARWICK UNIVERSITY

Vietnam in the CPTPP: The Trade-off between Trade and Public Health

MYUNG-HYUN CHUNG, KOREA UNIVERSITY LEGAL RESEARCH INSTITUTE

Patent Linkage and Its Implication under the CPTPP and the USMCA

SENTHIL KUMAR, BETHEL MEDICAL MISSION & HOSMAT HOSPITAL EDUCATIONAL GROUP, BANGALORE

Intellectual Property Rights in Physical Therapy Journals: A Systematic Survey

4.35pm – 5.00pm **Afternoon Tea Break** (*Auditorium Djokosoetono*)

PLENARY SESSION

Balai Sidang Djokosaetono

5.00pm –6.30 pm **THE IMPACT OF IP AND INNOVATION SCHOLARSHIP ON POLICY MAKING**

CHAIR

IRENE CALBOLI, TEXAS A&M UNIVERSITY SCHOOL OF LAW AND SCHOOL OF LAW,
UNIVERSITY OF GENEVA

PANELLISTS

ANTONY TAUBMAN, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY AND COMPETITION DIVISION,
WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION

K.D. RAJU, RAJIV GANDHI SCHOOL OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY LAW, INDIAN
INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, KHARAGPUR

MYUNG-HYUN CHUNG, KOREA UNIVERSITY LEGAL RESEARCH INSTITUTE

MASABUMI SUZUKI, GRADUATE SCHOOL OF LAW, NAGOYA UNIVERSITY

AGUS SARDJONO, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS INDONESIA

NAAZIMA KAMARDEEN, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF COLOMBO

7.00pm

Dinner and Cultural Performance

The Margo Hotel

END OF DAY 1 OF THE CONFERENCE

(See next page for the program of Day 2 of the Conference)

FRIDAY, 28 FEBRUARY 2020 (DAY 2)

8.00am – 9.00am **REGISTRATION**
Foyer Balai Sidang Djokosaetono

OPENING OF THE DAY

Balai Sidang Djokosaetono

9.00am – 9.05am SINGING OF THE INDONESIAN NATIONAL ANTHEM

9.05am – 9.10 am ***Welcome Remarks***
DR. EDMON MAKARIM
DEAN, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS INDONESIA

KEYNOTE PRESENTATION

Balai Sidang Djokosaetono

9.10am – 9.50am **I GUSTI AGUNG SUMANATHA**
JUSTICE OF THE SUPREME COURT, REPUBLIC OF INDONESIA

9.50am – 10.00am PHOTO SESSION (*Staircase of Auditorium Djokosoetono*)

10.00am – 10.20am **Morning Tea Break** (*Auditorium Djokosoetono*)

PARALLEL SESSIONS (3)

10.20am – 12.00pm **PARALLEL SESSION 4.A: GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS: SCOPE AND TYPES OF PROTECTION**
Balai Sidang
Djokosaetono **CHAIR**
MIRANDA RISANG AYU PALAR, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS PADJADJARAN
PRESENTERS
REBECCA FERDERER, GRADUATE SCHOOL OF LAW, NAGOYA UNIVERSITY
Comparative Analysis of Regional Collective Trademark and Sui Generis GI Protection in Japan
NAAZIMA KAMARDEEN, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF COLOMBO
Enabling a Registration System to Protect Geographical Indications in Sri Lanka: Amendment or Interpretation?

ANANTHU S. HARI & K.D. RAJU, RAJIV GANDHI SCHOOL OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY LAW, INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, KHARAGPUR

Post-TRIPS Free Trade Agreements and TRIPS-Plus Geographical Indications Standards in Asia

PAULRAJ BRINDA, SCHOOL OF EXCELLENCE IN LAW, THE TAMIL NADU DR. AMBEDKAR LAW UNIVERSITY

Standardization of GI Protection as Stimulating Tool for Higher Economic Impact

10.20am – 12.00pm

C 105

PARALLEL SESSION 3.B: PATENTS AND ACCESS TO HEALTH (POST-TRIPS)

CHAIR

BRYAN MERCURIO, FACULTY OF LAW, THE CHINESE UNIVERSITY OF HONG KONG

PRESENTERS

PADMAJA WIJESOORIYA, FACULTY OF LAW, GENERAL SIR JOHN KOTELAWALA DEFENCE UNIVERSITY

A Crisis in Waiting: Access to Medicine under Intellectual Property Law

HELEN YU, CENTER FOR ADVANCED STUDIES IN BIOMEDICAL INNOVATION LAW, UNIVERSITY OF COPENHAGEN

Leveraging Research Failures to Accelerate Drug Discovery and Development

SADHANA SRIVASTAVA, INDIAN COUNCIL OF MEDICAL RESEARCH

Intellectual Property Policy Framework for Promoting Access to Health Care in Developing Countries with Focus on India

PARAMITA DASGUPTA, WEST BENGAL NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF JURIDICAL SCIENCES

Ensuring Universal Health Coverage in a Post-TRIPS India

10.20am – 12.00pm

C 106

PARALLEL SESSION 3.C: COMMERCIALIZATION OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

CHAIR

OWAIS SHAIKH, SHAHEED ZULFIQAR ALI BHUTTO UNIVERSITY OF LAW

PRESENTERS

HALIZA SHUKOR, UNIVERSITI SAINS ISLAM MALAYSIA

Intellectual Property Commercialisation in Malaysia's Public Research Institute

TARIQUE FAIYAZ, RAJIV GANDHI SCHOOL OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY LAW, INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, KHARAGPUR

Innovation, Technology Transfer, Global Intellectual Property Regime and the Current Debate on Climate Change

MUKESH RAWAT & K.D. RAJU, RAJIV GANDHI SCHOOL OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY LAW, INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, KHARAGPUR

The Role of Public Procurement in Stimulating Innovation: A Case Study of South East Asia

LILY EVELINA SITORUS, INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS LAW, UNIVERSITAS PRASETIYA MULYA

Commercialization of Intellectual Property Rights

10.20am – 12.00pm

Soemadipraja &
Taher

PARALLEL SESSION 3.D: TRADITIONAL KNOWLEDGE AND TRADITIONAL CULTURAL EXPRESSIONS

CHAIR

DAI YOKOMIZO, GRADUATE SCHOOL OF LAW, NAGOYA UNIVERSITY

PRESENTERS

RASHEED SHAIK, A.K.K. NEW LAW ACADEMY

The Role of Biological Diversity, Traditional Knowledge and Intellectual Property Rights

AJOY JOSE, RAJIV GANDHI SCHOOL OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY LAW, INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, KHARAGPUR

Traditional Knowledge – The Changing Scenario in India

YULIA YULIA & S. AG FAISAL, FACULTY OF LAW, MALIKUSSALEH UNIVERSITY

The Protection of Traditional Knowledge under Indonesian Patent Law between Opportunities and Challenges

SHAMBHU PRASAD CHAKRABARTY, WEST BENGAL NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF JURIDICAL STUDIES

Unravelling the Traditional Knowledge Protection in India: The Supremacy of the East

10.20am – 12.00pm

F 103

PARALLEL SESSION 3.E: PATENTS AND PLANT VARIETIES

CHAIR

MASSIMILIANO GRANIERI, DEPARTMENT OF MECHANICAL AND INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF BRESCIA

PRESENTERS

DANIEL ASTONE, FACULTY OF LAW, STOCKHOLM UNIVERSITY

Framing Neglected Tropical Diseases as a Legal Research Problem

DEVA PRASAD M., INDIAN INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT, KOZHIKODE & **SUCHITRA MENON C.**, SAI UNIVERSITY, CHENNAI

Probing the Plant Variety Protection Law and Regulatory Conundrum in the Indian Context

AGUS LANINI, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS TADULAKO

Protection of Indigenous People's Rights over Genetic Resources around the Loro Lindu National Park

MAFRUZA SULTANA, FACULTY OF LEGAL STUDIES, SOUTH ASIAN UNIVERSITY

Legal Regime of Plant Varieties in International Law and Bangladesh

10.20am – 12.00pm

F 104

PARALLEL SESSION 3.F: COPYRIGHT AND ONLINE CONTENT

CHAIR

TATSUHIRO UENO, LAW SCHOOL, WASEDA UNIVERSITY

PRESENTERS

BASHAR MALKAWI, COLLEGE OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF SHARJAH

Online Piracy: The Egyptian Movie Industry and Copyright Enforcement

RANJIT ABRAHAM & P.J. YESU NESA JOY SINGH, SCHOOL OF EXCELLENCE IN LAW,
THE TAMI NADU DR. AMBEDKAR LAW UNIVERSITY

Interface between Digital Rights Management and Fair Use for Access to Information

APOORV CHAUDHARY, NATIONAL LAW UNIVERSITY, DELHI

Copyright in Video Games: Is there a Need for a Sui Generis System in India?

THARINDU RATHNAYAKE, DEPARTMENT OF MARKETING MANAGEMENT, THE OPEN
UNIVERSITY OF SRI LANKA

*Copyright Information Visibility and Copyright Awareness in Social Media:
Empirical Evidence from Sri Lanka*

10.20am – 12.00pm

F 105

PARALLEL SESSION 3.G: COPYRIGHT PROTECTION AND MUSIC

CHAIR

SEAN O'CONNOR, ANTONIN SCALIA LAW SCHOOL, GEORGE MASON UNIVERSITY

PRESENTERS

VISHWAS DEVAIAH, JINDAL GLOBAL LAW SCHOOL, O.P. JINDAL GLOBAL
UNIVERSITY

*Is there a Need to Differentiate between Internet Broadcasting of Music and Radio or
Television Broadcasting?*

ZIANA MAHFUZZAH, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS SUMATERA UTARA

*Duties and Authorities of Indonesian Collective Management Organization as a
Royalty Management for Songs and Music Contains in Digital Music Services*

PAUL SUGDEN, MONASH BUSINESS SCHOOL, MONASH UNIVERSITY

*Chinese Interpretations of Copyright Infringement in Music Compared with Australia
and USA-Two Tones or Tales?*

ROZA SIYUM GETACHEW, SCHOOL OF LAW, WOLLO UNIVERSITY

*The Role of Copyright Law in Promoting Gender Equality in Ethiopian Music: The
Case of Folk Music*

12.00pm – 2.30pm

Lunch (*Auditorium Djokosoetono*) **& Time for Friday Prayer**

PARALLEL SESSIONS (4)

2.30pm – 4.35pm

Balai Sidang

Djokosaetono

PARALLEL SESSION 4.A: DATA PROTECTION AND INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

RIGHTS

CHAIR

AGUS SARDJONO, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS INDONESIA

PRESENTERS

JAYANTA GHOSH, WEST BENGAL NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF JURIDICAL SCIENCES

*Data Protection and Big Data Security of Public Health: Comparative Approach of
US and India*

TAKESHI MAEDA, GRADUATE SCHOOL OF LAW, KOBE UNIVERSITY

Data Transaction and Protection of Data under Intellectual Property Law

SEAN O'CONNOR, ANTONIN SCALIA LAW SCHOOL, GEORGE MASON UNIVERSITY

Global Listener Data and Next Generation Music Production

SAEEDAH MAZINANIAN & YAVARI ASADOLLAH, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF SHAHID BEHESHTI

Privacy in Cyberspace: Islamic Republic of Iran Perspective

CHRISTIAN ANDERSEN & KOTA HAGIWARA, FACULTY OF LAW, MARANATHA CHRISTIAN UNIVERSITY

Data protection and Network Effect Concerning Monopoly and Privacy in the Digital Disruption Era in Indonesia

2.30am – 4.35pm

C 105

PARALLEL SESSION 4.B: TRADEMARKS, ENFORCEMENT, AND CULTURAL EXPRESSIONS

CHAIR

HENNY MARLYNA, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS INDONESIA

PRESENTERS

PUTROM SIAGIAN, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS SUMATERA UTARA

Liability of E-Commerce Platform for the Sale of Counterfeit Goods in Digital Era

ALAKNANDA SINGH, ICAI LAW SCHOOL, JAIPUR

Counterfeiting of Brands in India: Revisiting Existing Law and Analysis of Enforcement System

AGUNG SUJATMIKO, FACULTY OF LAW, AIRLANGGA UNIVERSITY

Legal Protection of Trademark in Kediri Small and Medium Entrepreneur

PRASETYO HADI PURWANDOKO, FACULTY OF LAW, SEBELAS MARET UNIVERSITY SURAKARTA

The Implementation of the Protection of Traditional Cultural Expression in Indonesia Based on Article 38 of Law 28/2014 Regarding Copyright

CHIH-CHIEH YANG, INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, NATIONAL YUNLIN UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY

How to Protect the Traditional Intellectual Creations of Indigenous People? Registration System and Fair Use

2.30pm – 4.35pm

C 106

PARALLEL SESSION 4.C: COMPARATIVE PERSPECTIVES ON PATENT LAW

CHAIR

SHAMBHU PRASAD CHAKRABARTY, WEST BENGAL NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF JURIDICAL STUDIES

PRESENTERS

MARTIN ADELMAN, GEORGE WASHINGTON UNIVERSITY LAW SCHOOL

The Tangential Exception to Prosecution History Estoppel in the US

QI JUN KWONG, GRADUATE SCHOOL OF LAW, NAGOYA UNIVERSITY
Patent of Importation: Historical Remnant or Viable Alternative to a “World Patent?”

SOUMYA PATRA, RAJIV GANDHI SCHOOL OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY LAW,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, KHARAGPUR
Intellectual Property Changes and Its Effects on Patent Filing in India

JUN TOMITA, GRADUATE SCHOOL OF LAW, WASEDA UNIVERSITY
Introducing Indirect Patent Infringement in China: The Japanese Experience

ANEESH PILLAI, SCHOOL OF LEGAL STUDIES, COCHIN UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY
*Interoperation of Competition Law and Intellectual Property Rights: A Comparative
Study of Asian Legal Systems with Special Reference to India*

2.30pm – 4.35pm
Soemadipraja &
TaHER

PARALLEL SESSION 4.D: INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY AND DISPUTE RESOLUTION

CHAIR

JACQUES DE WERRA, SCHOOL OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF GENEVA

PRESENTERS

PRENKESHA MENIA, SYMBIOSIS LAW SCHOOL, PUNE

Intellectual Property Right Disputes at International Level and Modes of Resolution

SHIHO KATO, GRADUATE SCHOOL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES, HIROSHIMA UNIVERSITY

Cross-Border Injunctions in Japanese IP Cases

CHARU DUREJA, RAYAT COLLEGE OF LAW, PANJAB UNIVERSITY CHANDIGARH

*Arbitration is an Alternative and Not a Primary Method for Intellectual Property
Right Dispute Resolution in India*

PIERGIUSEPPE PUSCEDDU, TILBURG LAW AND ECONOMICS CENTER, THE
UNIVERSITY OF TILBURG

The Use of Arbitration to Settle FRAND Disputes, with Focus on China

DAI YOKOMIZO, GRADUATE SCHOOL OF LAW, NAGOYA UNIVERSITY

Cross-Border Trade Secret Disputes – Analysis by Conflict of Laws

2.30pm – 5.00pm
F 103

PARALLEL SESSION 4.E: COMPARATIVE PERSPECTIVES ON COPYRIGHT LAW

CHAIR

MOHAMED ABDERRAOUF BDILOU, WIPO ACADEMY, WORLD INTELLECTUAL
PROPERTY ORGANIZATION

PRESENTERS

AMEYA PANT, DMD ADVOCATES, & **DIPESH JAIN**, BOMBAY HIGH COURT

Intellectual Property Right Protection and Obscenity: An Indian Perspective

ANJANA GIRISH, INTER UNIVERSITY CENTRE FOR INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS
STUDIES, COCHIN UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Visually Impaired Persons and Access to Copyrighted Works: The Indian Road Map

AMIT JAMSANDEKAR, FACULTY OF LAW, LEICESTER UNIVERSITY

Copyright-A New Regime in India

SAMUEL ANDREWS, UNIVERSITY OF GONDAR SCHOOL OF LAW

Unpacking the Intersectionality of IP Limitations Jurisprudence and the Marrakesh Treaty: Disabilities and Expressions in Copyright of Ethiopia, Nigeria and USA

M. AFZAL WANI, SCHOOL OF LAW AND LEGAL STUDIES, GURU GOBIND SINGH INDRAPRASTHA UNIVERSITY

Unauthorised Publishing and Dubious Photo-Copying of Books in the Name of Academics in Developing Countries: Looking for Solutions for Authors' Concerns

LUCKY GEORGE & AARTHI RATHNA R., SCHOOL OF EXCELLENCE IN LAW, THE TAMIL NADU DR. AMBEDKAR LAW UNIVERSITY

Reverse Engineering of Copyrighted Computer Program: A Comparative Study

2.30pm – 4.35pm

F 104

PARALLEL SESSION 4.F: INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY, INNOVATION, AND MANAGEMENT

CHAIR

VALERIY LISITSA, DEPARTMENT OF BUSINESS LAW, CIVIL AND ARBITRATION PROCEDURE, NOVOSIBIRSK STATE UNIVERSITY

PRESENTERS

MAYUREE SENGUPTA, INDIAN INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT, KASHIPUR

IP as an Indicator of Innovation: A Review

AJAY KUMAR SHARMA, RAJIV GANDHI SCHOOL OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY LAW, INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, KHARAGPUR

Criminal Law Enforcement in Counterfeit and Piracy to Benefit Innovations and Protect IP: Problems and Perspectives

NIHARIKA SALAR, FACULTY OF LAW, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF SINGAPORE

Critical Analysis of Passing Off Jurisprudence in Celebrities: An Indian Perspective

M. SAKTHIVEL, SCHOOL OF LAW AND LEGAL STUDIES, GURU GOBIND SINGH INDRAPRASTHA UNIVERSITY

Taxation of IP Assets in India: Need for a Rational Approach?

RANJEET KUMAR, DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING, MADANAPALLE INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY & SCIENCE, CHITTOOR

Impact of IP Generation and Technology Management at the Higher Educational Universities in the Developing Countries

2.30pm – 5.00pm

F 105

PARALLEL SESSION 4.G: PATENTS AND PHARMACEUTICALS: COMPARATIVE PERSPECTIVES

CHAIR

KIYOSHI ADACHI, NATIONAL GRADUATE INSTITUTE FOR POLICY STUDIES

PRESENTERS

FRANTZESKA PAPADOPOULOU, FACULTY OF LAW, STOCKHOLM UNIVERSITY

Regulatory Rights in the Pharmaceutical Industry; A System in Flux? The EU Experience and the Possibility to Make Things Different in the Future?!

KANIKARAM SATYANARAYANA, INDIAN COUNCIL OF MEDICAL RESEARCH

Access to Affordable Health Care: Some Strategies to Overcome IP and other Barriers to Promote Access to Biosimilars with Focus on Developing Countries

SHIRIN SYED, KAVAYITRI BAHINABAI CHAUDHARI NORTH MAHARASHTRA UNIVERSITY

Patent and Generic Availability: A Case Study of HIV, HCV and TB Medicines in India

MOHAMMAD ATATUR RAHMAN & OWAIS SHAIKH, SHAHEED ZULFIQAR ALI BHUTTO UNIVERSITY OF LAW

Protecting Pharmaceutical Patents in Pakistan

K.M. GOPAKUMAR, THIRD WORLD NETWORK

Patents and Innovation: Post TRIPS Behaviour of Indian Pharmaceutical Companies

JUSTYNA OZEGALSKA-TRYBALSKA, FACULTY OF LAW, JAGIELLONIAN UNIVERSITY

A New SPC Regulation in Europe and its Possible Impact on the Pharmaceutical Sector and the Access to Medicines in the EU and Third Countries

4.45pm – 5.15pm **Afternoon Tea Break** (*Auditorium Djokosoetono*)

CLOSING REMARKS

Balai Sidang Djokosaetono

5.15pm – 5.45pm **AGUS SARDJONO**, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS INDONESIA
MOHAMED ABDERRAOUF BDIQUI, WIPO ACADEMY, WORLD INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY ORGANIZATION
ANTONY TAUBMAN, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY, GOVERNMENT PROCUREMENT AND COMPETITION DIVISION, WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION
JACQUES DE WERRA, SCHOOL OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF GENEVA
IRENE CALBOLI, TEXAS A&M UNIVERSITY SCHOOL OF LAW AND SCHOOL OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF GENEVA

5.45pm – 7.30pm **Reception** (*Auditorium Djokosoetono*)
Sponsored by International Trademark Association (INTA)

CONCLUSION OF THE CONFERENCE (*See next page for the program of the Workshop*)

Workshop Program

SATURDAY, 29 FEBRUARY 2020

8.30am – 9.00am **REGISTRATION**
Foyer Balai Sidang Djokosaetono

WELCOME REMARKS

Balai Sidang Djokosaetono

9.00am – 9.05 am **AGUS SARDJONO**, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS INDONESIA
IRENE CALBOLI, TEXAS A&M UNIVERSITY SCHOOL OF LAW AND SCHOOL OF LAW,
UNIVERSITY OF GENEVA
JACQUES DE WERRA, SCHOOL OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF GENEVA

FIRST SESSION

9.05am –10.40am **WHAT ARE CURRENT, RELEVANT, AND IMPACTFUL RESEARCH TOPICS?**

CHAIR

JACQUES DE WERRA, SCHOOL OF LAW, UNIVERSITY OF GENEVA

PANELLISTS

OWAIS SHAIKH, SHAHEED ZULFIQAR ALI BHUTTO UNIVERSITY OF LAW

MIRANDA RISANG AYU PALAR, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS PADJADJARAN

SEAN O’CONNOR, ANTONIN SCALIA LAW SCHOOL, GEORGE MASON UNIVERSITY

SANG JO JONG, SEOUL NATIONAL UNIVERSITY SCHOOL OF LAW

HA LE THI THU, FACULTY OF ECONOMICS AND INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS,
FOREIGN TRADE UNIVERSITY

10.40am – 11.10am **Tea Break** (*Foyer Balai Sidang Djokosaetono*)

SECOND SESSION

11.10am –12.45pm **RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES: WHAT AND HOW TO CHOOSE?**

CHAIR

IRENE CALBOLI, TEXAS A&M UNIVERSITY SCHOOL OF LAW AND SCHOOL OF LAW,
UNIVERSITY OF GENEVA

PANELLISTS

GREGORY N. MANDEL, BEASLEY SCHOOL OF LAW, TEMPLE UNIVERSITY

AGUS SARDJONO, FACULTY OF LAW, UNIVERSITAS INDONESIA

IDA MADIEHA ABDUL GHANI AZMI, AHMAD IBRAHIM KULLIYAH OF LAWS,
INTERNATIONAL ISLAMIC UNIVERSITY MALAYSIA

BRYAN MERCURIO, FACULTY OF LAW, CHINESE UNIVERSITY OF HONG KONG

MYUNG-HYUN CHUNG, KOREA UNIVERSITY LEGAL RESEARCH INSTITUTE

12.45pm – 2.00pm **Lunch** (*Auditorium Djokosoetono*)

CONCLUSION OF THE WORKSHOP